

ENERGY HARVESTING OF DIELECTRIC ELASTOMERS AS FUNCTIONS OF SPECIMEN GEOMETRIES, CONSTITUENT AND LOADING TYPE.

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ABSTRACT

The energy harvesting performance of an EADE (Electro-active dielectric elastomer) is studied as functions of constituent content, specimen geometries and types of loading. The used constituents are thinner and ferroelectric ceramic filler (BaTiO_3) for the elastomer; carbon black(CB), MWCNT and BaTiO_3 for the electrode. Both elastomer and electrode are made of the same material (silicon rubber) for excellent durability, linearity and repeatability. After obtained the best condition of fillers content for electrode with the specific resistance of $73 \Omega\text{cm}$, the measured output voltage was measured depending on the specimen thickness, layer, thinner & BaTiO_3 content of elastomer, degree of strain under the compression and flexural loadings. It is found that the measured output voltage at a given strain increases with the specimen thickness ($0.25 \rightarrow 2 \text{ mm}$) and layer number($1 \rightarrow 3$). Also, as the thinner increases from 0 to 30 wt. %, the output voltage reaches the maximum around 15 wt. %. And, BaTiO_3 content increases from 0 to 75 wt. %, the output voltage increases due to their inherent piezoelectric properties. In general, the results show a good agreement with a simple prediction model that based on the Maxwell stress theory. The output voltage should be related with a square root of the compressive strain and the modulus of the polymer-electrode and with a direct relationship to the specimen thickness.

1. INTRODUCTION

Piezoelectric materials have demonstrated the ability to harness ambient vibrations for use as sensors and generators and have been incorporated into many energy-scavenging designs. However, the main limitations imposed by piezoelectric ceramics are their stiffness, brittleness and cost. They are suitable for applications where the ambient energy is in the form of small-amplitude high-frequency vibrations. On the other hand, the electro-active polymers refer to the broad class of polymeric materials capable of responding to electrical stimuli possess the general advantage of being mechanically flexible, lightweight and easy processing.

Especially, recent advances in dielectric elastomer (DE) technology could enable a new generation of energy harvesting devices with high efficiency and low cost. Dielectric elastomers, known as electronic polymers, have shown considerable promise for harvesting energy from environmental sources such as ocean waves, wind, water currents, human motion, etc. The high energy density and conversion efficiency of DE can allow for very simple and robust 'direct drive' generators. Various types of energy harvesting generators based on DE have been designed and tested recently. [1-3]

For DE generators, certain material parameters are of greater importance, including the resistivity of the dielectric and resistance of the electrodes. The ideal DE material should have high energy density, low viscoelastic loss, and overcome dielectric and mechanical failure as a result of fatigue after the repeated deformation as a part of system. To maximize the functional properties of the ferroelectric polymer, ferroelectric ceramic inclusion such as BaTiO_3 , PbTiO_3 can be embedded in the elastomeric matrix as a filler to enhance the desired functional properties. These ceramic inclusions are conventional ferroelectric materials which exhibit a high dielectric permittivity as well as large spontaneous polarization. Furthermore, the remarkable piezoelectric, pyroelectric and ferroelectric

properties of these ceramic fillers, together with the high degree of flexibility of the polymer component have offered a promising potential for functional electronic application. [4-6]

Silicone materials show promise for energy harvesting purposes as they generally possess a wide operating temperature range, which is important for most applications, low viscoelasticity, and are generally resistant to many environmental factors, including moisture. Silicone rubbers, however, are known to have lower energy densities owing to their lower breakdown fields when compared to highly pre-strained VHB acrylic elastomers.[7] However, the silicone rubber is used for dielectric elastomer and compliant electrode since using same materials gives much better adhesion and endurance under a repeated actuation. To achieve this goal, the fillers such as CB, CNT, BaTiO₃ and the thinner are used to optimize the actuation and mechanical properties. [8-9]

Although the design specifications and power harvesting capabilities of most piezoelectric energy harvesting systems are not trivial, any vibrating/mechanical host presents the possibility of harvesting energy. The application of piezoelectric materials in power harvesting systems contains many variables which can be manipulated to obtain electrical energy from ambient mechanical energy. For a floor tile/shoe sole as DE energy harvester under the compressive loading, this developmental work needs to determine the ideal DE material and the ideal structural material to allow for the maximum power generation while maintaining a good flexibility and conformability.

The purpose of this paper is a study of the effect of stain amplitude, specimen geometries, BaTiO₃/thinner content and loading type to maximize the energy density of the silicone rubber that is a basic material for both electrode and matrix.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

For flexible electrode, the matrix for experimental studies was a RTV (room temperature vulcanization) type silicone KE-12 (viscosity: 100 poise at 25°C) from Shin-Etsu chemical Co., Ltd. The multi-walled CNTs (CM-100 =10~15nm from Hanwha Nanotech Co., Ltd.) and conductive CB (Conductex SC Ultra from Saehan Silicem Co., Ltd.) are used as reinforcing carbon materials and other ingredients of commercial-grade quality.[9] The homogenizer and stirrer are used to mix the CNT and CB. The nonvolatile thinner for RTV is used to control the viscosity. The dispersion of CNTs involves the dissolution of CNTs in toluene in order to disentangle the nano-tubes that typically tend to cling together and form lumps, rendering them difficult to process. For this phase, 5 g of CNTs was added to 400ml of toluene using a weighing balance. This solution was further sonicated for 1 hr. using a mechanical sonicator (Vibra Cell, Sonic & Material Co.) that was capable of vibrating at ultrasonic frequencies (750Watts, 20kHz) in order to induce an efficient dispersion of CNTs. If needed, the sonicating time is increased for 30 min. And then, the mixture is dried for 24 hr. at 80 °C. Finally, to mix the CNTs (1.74 wt. %), CB(8.93 wt. %), thinner (39.73 wt %) and KE-12 rubber solution(49.6 wt.%), a mixing machine (IKA Ultra-Turrax T-25 Digital) was used for 1 hr. at 10,000rpm. Based on previous works, this electrode has the specific resistance of 73 Ωcm. The matrix was also silicone KE-12 from the same company. As a piezoelectric filler, BaTiO₃ was added up to 75 wt. %. Also, thinner was added up to 35 wt. % to optimize the mixing condition with other fillers. The vacuum time for each process was 5 minutes and the total curing time of the specimen for each condition was 8 hours. After mixing the matrix for 30 min., a primary vacuum was applied. The second vacuum was carried out after adding the hardener (0.5 wt. %) to the mixture. The mixture was poured into the mold (60 mm x 60 mm for compression tests and 260 & 130mm x 210 & 105 mm for flexural loading). The third vacuum was applied. The vacuum time for each process was 5 minutes and the total curing time of the specimen for each condition was 8 hours. And then, the electrode (40 mm x 40 mm for compression, and 220 & 110 mm x 170 & 85 mm for flexural loadings) is painted in the middle of elastomer. And, the specimen is dried for 12 hr. before connecting the electric wire.

2.2 Testing methods

Compression tests with cylindrical resin indenter (30 mm in diameter) were tested in a LRY Plus (LLOYD Co. Ltd.) testing machine with a loading speed of 50 mm/min as shown in Fig. 1. Fig. 2 shows the flexural test equipment that can control the frequency of 0.5~10 Hz and amplitude of 10 mm~70 mm. All reported data are the average of three specimens that are tested at a same condition.

Figure 1: Compression test

Figure 2: Flexural test

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The measured mechanical properties of electrode and elastomer that tested in this studies are given in references [8,9]. In general, the tensile modulus and dielectric constant of NBR are higher than KE-12 silicone rubber. During these tests, it is found that the data of measured voltage value shows a large scattering as the thickness of specimen and the number of layer increase. The specimen over $t=3$ mm is tried and not included since the result is not reliable.

Figure 3: The experimentally measured output voltage during loading

Figure 4: The measured output voltage as functions of compressive strain and thickness.

Fig. 3 shows the real data of output voltage during the compressive loadings and presented voltage values after averaging many cycles. After the stabilizing in the beginning stage, the measured voltage is reasonably consistent. Fig. 4 shows the measured output voltage as functions of compressive strain and thickness with 2 layers. The measured voltage at constant strain increases with the specimen thickness. To understand this data, the tensile mode of DE is assumed to be same phenomenon as the compressive mode. It is known [10] that the strain exhibited by a DE depends on its modulus, boundary conditions, and external loading. For small strains under free boundary conditions, the thickness strain, ϵ , can be written as

$$\varepsilon = \frac{-p}{E} = -\mu\mu_0 V^2 / (Et^2) \quad (1)$$

where μ_0 is the permittivity of free space, μ is the dielectric constant of the material, V is the applied voltage, t is the polymer thickness and E is the modulus of elasticity of the polymer-electrode composite. For multiple layers (n) of DE with the same thickness which are piled up, the total deformation (Δ_t) can be

$$\Delta_t = \sum_{i=0}^n \Delta_i = n \varepsilon t \quad (2)$$

By combing Eqns. (1) and (2), the output voltage can be assumed as

$$V \approx \sqrt{\frac{Et\Delta_t}{n\mu\mu_0}} = \sqrt{\frac{E\varepsilon t^2}{\mu\mu_0}} \quad (3)$$

As seen in Eqn. (3) and Fig. 4, the output voltage should be related with a square root of the compressive strain and with a direct relationship to the specimen thickness. Also, the output voltage should be related with a square root of the modulus of the electrode-elastomer composite and with inversely proportion to square root of the dielectric constant. However, as seen in Fig. 4, there is a large difference between $t=1.0$ mm and $t=1.5$ mm even though the voltage is changing with a square root of the compressive strain. Also, it is observed that the obtained voltage has a large scattering as the specimen thickness gets thicker. Both need a further investigation.

Figure 5: The measured output voltage as functions of the number of layer and strain for the specimen with $t=1$ mm.

Figure 6: The effects of BaTiO_3 content (wt. %) at a given strain.

Fig. 5 shows the measured voltage as functions of the layer number and strain with the specimen of $t=1.0$ mm. In general, as the number of layer increases, the obtained voltage shows a large scattering. Even though the rate of increase is different for the given thickness, the voltage increases with number of layer. Based on Figs. 4 and 5, it is possible to select the optimal parameters of products depending on applications under the compressive loading. Fig. 6 shows the measured voltage depending on the content of BaTiO_3 on the elastomer at a given strain. As the BaTiO_3 content increases, the modulus and the dielectric constant of the specimen increase. However, a large increase in output voltage between $\varepsilon=20\%$ and $\varepsilon=30\%$ and a relationship between dielectric constant and modulus need a further study.

Figure 7: The effects of thinner content (wt. %) at a given strain.

Fig. 7 shows the effects of the thinner content on the output voltage. In general, as the thinner content increases, the modulus of the specimen decreases. Therefore, the output voltage is expected to decrease. However, the measured voltage increases up to 15 wt. % and then decreases even though the value of dielectric constant decreases with the thinner content. Therefore, it is expected that there are an optimum range of thinner content as seen in this figure. Also, the other types of filler can be added to improve mechanical and energy aspects. However, there should be the ideal condition for DE material that shows high energy density, low viscoelastic loss, and overcome dielectric and mechanical failure in various applications.

Since many applications of energy harvesting are feasible with a bending of clamped plate. In this study, the flexural test under the concentrated loading is used as shown in Fig. 2. In general, the experimentally obtained data shows a larger scattering than the data by the compressive test. The measured output voltage as functions of amplitude and thickness is shown in Fig. 8. In general, as the specimen thickness increases, the voltage increases especially with large amplitude.

Figure 8: The measured output voltage as functions of amplitude and thickness

Figure 9: The measured output voltage as functions of frequency and thickness with Amplitude=25 mm

Also, as expected, the frequency increase leads to a low output voltage. However, the specimen thickness affects differently as shown in Figs. 8 and 9. Both loading cases give a high output with $t=2.0$ mm.

4. CONCLUSIONS

From this study, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. As the specimen thickness increases, the measured output voltage at constant strain increases. In general, the output voltage should be related with a direct relationship to the specimen thickness. The optimum specimen geometries depending on applications should be studied in each application.
2. The measured output voltage increases as the content of BaTiO₃ and the number of layer increases.
3. The specimen with 15 wt. % of thinner has the maximum output voltage. Since the output voltage can be related with a square root of the modulus of the electrode-elastomer composite and with inversely proportion to square root of the dielectric constant of used materials. For engineering applications, the silicone rubber with reinforcing fillers should be modified to increase the energy harvesting.
4. The measured output voltage increases with amplitude and decreases with frequency.
5. Generally, the results show a good agreement with the predictions of a simple model that based on the Maxwell stress theory.

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